

**FACTORS FOR FORMING THE ATTITUDE OF
TOLERANCE IN STUDENTS**

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Annotation: Tolerance is not concession, discrimination or pretension, but above all, an active attitude formed on the basis of recognition of universal human rights and fundamental freedoms. This article talks about the formation and development of tolerant attitude among students.

Key words: xenophobia, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

INTRODUCTION

The problem of inter-ethnic relations and inter-ethnic tolerance is one of the most urgent problems. Xenophobia is most acutely manifested among young people, including students, which is confirmed by the sociology of youth and the sociology of education. Therefore, all scientists, cultural and enlightened people should understand how much responsibility they have for the problems of educating the population in the spirit of mutual respect and national tolerance, striving to understand the history, culture and national characteristics of peoples. They have been living in the neighborhood for centuries. For example, our country is one of the largest multinational countries of the modern world, which unites different nationalities with its unique culture. Later, moral values, which are not characteristic of the Muslim society and culture, began to be brought up in the minds of the youth of our country. Student youth mainly determines the vector of future changes of society. Students demonstrate the development of personal potential, professionalism and skills in solving problems at any state level. Therefore, promoting the ideas of tolerance among students as the most active social group called to further establish dialogic relations between different peoples

and cultures is the most urgent task. Students have a special place in the society due to the fact that they have a high level of professional and personal culture, are ready to participate in the process of changing our country and act as real partners of state bodies, legislative and executive authorities. At all levels of solving social, educational and other problems, the state, in turn, should openly declare its position towards young people, using their high potential, which is not fully implemented at the moment. The establishment of the Youth Tolerance School will be an important step in creating and testing a model of intercultural cooperation among young people, in the process of forming a civil society, and in educating young people in the spirit of respect for the culture of different peoples. It creates a foundation for the formation of socially active student youth and increases the civic engagement of students.

Originally, the term meant tolerance and acceptance of something or someone. When studying this term in this context, it is necessary to define some limits of tolerance and acceptance. The tolerant attitude of the student to the teacher, the relationship between students of different courses (for example, the contrast between "new and old"), specialties - in general, in any small groups, one can talk about elementary politeness. But in this case, we need to consider a more precise definition that reveals the essence of tolerance as a social phenomenon: tolerance is a sincere, consciously respectful tolerance, aimed at accepting with respect the ethnic, religious independence of others, other cultures specific psychological attitude, customs and way of life, moral values, ideological beliefs and views, manifestation of human individuality, respected, connected with an active psychological process, interreligious, aimed at overcoming or weakening inter-ethnic and internal independent psychological factors, general, interpersonal relations and the desire to live peacefully and understand each other, and it is necessary to pay attention to another definition: "tolerance" in UN documents - it is the recognition, respect and observance of the rights and freedoms of all people, regardless of social, class, religious, ethnic or other characteristics. Cultivating

tolerance is directly related to solving the problems of extremism, Nazism, and religious conflicts. This process can be accompanied by an increase in the manifestation of various prejudices and fears in the public mind: xenophobia, ethnophobia, Caucasian phobia and anti-Semitism, migrant phobia, nationalism, as a reaction to meeting a foreign person or culture. discrimination and intolerance. Thus, in the context of growing social diversity in society, there is a dangerous trend of increasing inter-ethnic, inter-religious, socio-economic, inter-generational and political intolerance. Such forms of intolerance are often used by extremist currents that incite hatred, national enmity and social conflicts in society.

Enterprises in the conditions of modernization of the economy of our country. In the economic sphere, the pragmatic function of tolerance as a social norm determining the balance of interests of competing parties is manifested with particular clarity. For example, in the negotiation process, any intolerance or simply not being ready for tolerance will lead to failure. Thus, the analysis of the influence of the role of negotiation culture as a manifestation of social tolerance norms is required not only to increase tolerance of different layers of society towards each other and to develop a social strategy. The fight against extremism, but also to qualitatively increase the efficiency of the modern economy. The third situation concerns the role in the fight against discrimination, racism, xenophobia and related intolerance, extremism and terrorism in the international legal space, which is impossible without observing the declaration of principles of tolerance. The problem of tolerance among students is one of the most surprising problems, because when people start studying at universities, they encounter many foreign people with different beliefs, cultures, appearance and outlook on life. Therefore, it is necessary to explain to the child that there are many people in the world, they are all different from each other, but at the same time they have equal rights to live from early childhood. On the other hand, in grades 1-7, who had an issue of intolerance towards another nationality or religion? However, in the first 3 years of a person's life, he gets the basic knowledge about the world, so at this

time, it is necessary to teach the child tolerance, because it will be manifested at a later age. It is ineffective to teach a child to be tolerant, but not to tolerate yourself. Imagine if a father explains to his son that there are representatives of different nationalities and that they should be treated with tolerance, but at the same time insults the market workers and uses obscene words against citizens of another nationality! Out of prudence, the child listens to this information like any parent's instruction, but it is unlikely that he will carry it out in life. First of all, education plays an equally important role here. Tolerance should be instilled as early as possible, but it is unlikely to talk about school age, when such concepts are simply uninteresting and incomprehensible. According to psychological research, the optimal age period for the formation of socio-cultural tolerance as a moral quality of a person is adolescence, which includes students. It should be recognized that the most advanced, organized, intellectually and creatively developed part of the youth is the student body. Student youth mainly determines the vector of future changes of society. For the student, tolerance refers to relationships within the student environment and, of course, outside of it. These relationships are very difficult to control because they depend on each person's personal culture.

Thus, it is necessary not only to promote the idea of tolerance, but also to increase the level of general cultural development of students. Students listen to their peers faster than the older generation. The best way to build tolerant relations is to listen to young people and talk to them as equals, the most effective way. If we use this way effectively, we will be able to educate the generation that our president said in the future.

Literature

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